

**METAPHORS OF NATURAL PHENOMEN IN TOURISTIC
ADVERTISING NARRATIVES**

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Annotation: Structuring a figurative view of the world of tourist destinations, creating a mythopoetic dream, promotional tourist narrative as mythologized text exhibits a high degree of metaphor. The article considers some aspects of metaphorisation of natural phenomena, which are represented by spatial, temporal and procedural, perceptual, visual, tactile, connotative, coloristic, anthropomorphic and other characteristics.

Key words: touristic advertising narrative; local interests; metaphor; natural disasters.

Structuring a figurative representation of the world of tourist destination, creating a mythopoetic daydream, tourist narrative of advertising as a mythologized text shows a high degree of metaphoricalness. The article studies some aspects of the metaphorization of natural phenomena, which are represented by spatial, temporal - procedural, perceptual, visual, tactile, connotative, coloristic, anthropomorphic and other characteristics. An advertising tourism narrative is a discursive formation recorded in the form of text, which is a way of creating a world of local interest in the form of tourist plot-narrative events occurring within a certain space-time framework [Menshikova E.E 2012]. Speaking about the “world of local interest” we mean a fragment of the picture of the world, including geographical, sociocultural, sociomental content and characteristic of a certain place, which in our case is a tourist destination - a physical space that includes tourist products, touristic resources. This space has physical and administrative boundaries that determine the way it is managed, images and perceptions that determine its market competitiveness [Menshikova 2014]. The world of local interest, updated by the advertising tourism narrative, is a symbolic

image formed on the basis of emotional and rational ideas, associations in their geographical, ethnic, historical and cultural components.

About a thousand years ago, the islands of New Zealand began to be inhabited by people of the Pacific Ocean - the “people of the land” Maori. Before them, it was a land of unexplored forests, mountains and deserted beaches. The loudest sound was the song of a bird, the whistle of the wind, the splash of a wave and the echo of a falling stone. New Zealand is a land of contrasts and abundance... picturesque geysers and magical fjords, magnificent glaciers and soft beaches of golden sand, endless fertile plains and wild rocky coastlines, piercing mountains and vast oceans, grandiose waterfalls and fern-fringed river banks. Holidays in New Zealand are a real adventure... diving into the depths of the sea, soaring above the clouds, penetrating into the bowels of the earth in search of treasures. Holidays in New Zealand - the perfection of hospitality... excellent wines, a velvety palette of exquisite tastes of New Zealand cuisine, sophisticated social entertainment. Volcanic wonders, snowy mountain peaks, clear lakes, endless beaches of the North Island, theatrical fjords, majestic glaciers, turbulent mountain streams, impenetrable forests... ([gltour.ru>geo/new-zealand/](http://gltour.ru/geo/new-zealand/)). The world of local interest is mythopoetic at its core; it represents an interweaving of real features and imaginary ones, completed by the consciousness of the subjects of the tourist destination [Menshikova 2014]

According to F. Losev, - always mythical, the reason for which is living, spontaneous life itself with all its hopes and fears, expectations and despair, with all its everyday and purely personal interest” [Losev 1991: 26].

A. Agarkova, as the symbolic “lens” approaches regional loci, the space of national culture reveals the diversity of the cultural landscape, represented by specifically local mythopoetic symbolism and figurative themes [Agarkova 2002].

of thinking and the processes of creating not only a nationally specific vision of the world, but also its universal image. Metaphor thereby strengthened the connection with logic, on the one hand, and mythology, on the other” [Arutyunova 1999: 371].

P. Chudinov, “a metaphor can be perceived both as a word that has a figurative meaning, and as a process of metaphorical development of verbal semantics in a language or in a specific communicative situation; a metaphor is also called a whole

Metaphor has a transfer function, carried out on the basis of the basic concepts of linguistic consciousness and acts as a universal code for creating allegories, such as analogy, comparison, metonymy, synecdoche, allegory and other figures of transfer.

Metaphor participates in the process of forming new concepts, changes the everyday language of people, while simultaneously changing their perception of the world and ways of comprehending it [Baryshnikov 2008:16].

In this article we are talking about metaphors of natural phenomena.

Nature occupies an important place in the system of human knowledge and ideas about the world, being closely connected with the culture and mentality of the people.

Living and inanimate nature has long served man as a kind of model, according to which he represents social reality, thus creating a linguistic picture of the world [Chudinov 2003].

Nature is not only an object of figurative perception, allowing us to express the relationship between man and nature in the range from their opposition to unity, as well as in terms of emotional, evaluative, expressive perception: Holidays in the Seychelles are a sacred sacrament of nature.

The concept of “natural phenomena” is defined as “climatic conditions, as well as the external expression of the totality of natural conditions related to nature” [Chastikova 2009: 8]: celestial bodies (sun, moon, star, luminary), atmospheric phenomena (wind, thunder, heat, eclipse, sunset, drops (rain), ice, sky, cloud, snow, heat, light, thunderclap, cold, shadow, darkness, storm, whirlwind, thunderstorm, hail, rain, downpour, frost, flood, fog) and etc.

Natural phenomena subject to the semantic process of metaphorization in an advertising tourism narrative include celestial bodies and the celestial sphere, time of day, seasons, weather, air, climate, as well as unusual natural phenomena (for example, northern lights, star shower). Heavenly bodies. The celestial bodies include the sun,

moon and stars. They are characterized by such features as being in the sky, appearing during the day/night, geometric shape, movement across the sky, variations in appearance, source of light and heat, the presence of anthropomorphic features, coloristic characteristics, etc.

The Sun.

The sun is a visual-sensory image that is formed on the basis of visual and tactile perception.

The sun is often endowed with anthropomorphic signs and properties and acts as an active subject, capable of performing actions inherent in humans.

In addition, not only the sun itself is endowed with anthropomorphic characteristics and properties, but also various periods of its activity: sunrise, sunset, dawn, dawn.

In the tourism advertising narrative, the sun is metaphorically represented by spatial characteristics, temporal-processual characteristics, perceptual visual characteristics, tactile characteristics: The emerging mountains resemble a black and white child's photograph.

The sun smiled...(Iabirint.com.ru); Canary Islands.

Metaphor is assigned the role of intensifying the attractiveness of the tourist concept “destination”, or, in other words, metaphor participates in the formation of a positive image - the image of the destination” [Alikina 2010: 45].

LITERATURE

Agarkova A. A Mythopoetics as a way of creating an image of a region: Based on the material of Donbass: author's abstract. dis.... cand. cultural studies. Moscow, 2002

Alekseev K.I Metaphor as a means of denoting intentions in the text // Word in action.

Mishlanova S. L Attractive function of metaphor in tourist discourse // Bulletin of Perm University.